

DRAFT - PreBriefing, DeBriefing and Upshot

Talking an Education, A Framework for Enriching Engagement,

by K Moses, reach me at K.Moses@outlook.com,

6th February, 2020

Abstract

...I have a framework of sorts for running assignments developed in *Cancer Prevention* courses with junior and senior undergraduates, pre-med students and graduate students: (1)Assignment starts, (2)PreBriefings while it is running, After initial Responses, After peer-to-peer Responses - submissions are public to class - a (3)DeBriefing, and After Grading an (4)UpShot review(s) which can include student excerpts, [UnderConstruction]

Draft

Contents

Contents	1
Introduction	1
Notes	2
Praise Commentary	3
Next,	4
References	4

Introduction

Dears, I think I have a framework for guiding the doing of assignments and providing feedback on assignments, I feel it might be useful to others teaching; I need some teaching souls to read it and give feedback, Thanks,

- During the Autumn/Winter Semester 2019 I taught a course online called ‘Cancer Prevention;’ in face-to-face versions of similar courses I have used the techniques of *DeBriefing(s)* assignments - suggested, guided by *Sherrish Holloman and Laura Rigolosi, circa 2014* - and now in the online format I continue this method expanding to embrace ***PreBriefings***, *DeBriefing(s)* and an ***Upshot*** review.
 - Online I run all contents and assignments as Discussions in the BlackBoard (BB) Discussion platform, including extending the path for submissions to embrace work developed in Google Docs. I am supporting getting to a fourth draft described by John McPhee 2013. The collaborative options provided by Google Docs has aided this,
 - *Here is an aside*, I would love to find an open-source version of the BB Discussion Platform, also focusing on the creation of user Threads; I was not successful this Semester with getting the Class members to migrate to GitHub,
- The assignment schedule uses a Monday release, Thursday - an ***initial Response*** posted, Sunday - ***peer-to-peer Responses*** posted. For guidance see DCUEVAS1 2019. I tried to ensure members responded before seeing their peers’ initial posts by requesting posting within a 30 minute designated time window. My objective was for initial responses to be written without peer influence.
- The ***PreBriefing method*** is all in one *response thread by me*. I try for every day of a running assignment to share an ongoing analysis of the assignment with the Class members, trying to provide ***scaffoldings, clues for getting the assignment done and supporting the assignment as a relevant journey***.
- The ***timing of the DeBriefing*** depends on a guesstimate of the last peer-to-peer response, all discussions were kept open for the remaining duration of the course,
- If I mess-up that initial casting of an assignment or/and get the scaffolding wrong for engaging all Class members, e.g., wrong on *choices and relevancy*, ***PreBriefings allow me space to sort of fix things***,
 - *The take away from the semesters* that was most informative for building ***Learning Environments*** is the vital role of ***Praise Commentary*** in creating a ***community***, and the members are good at it. I interpret it as the contribution of deep, deep histories in ***Social Media*** are part of the members’ assets they are sharing with the Class,

Notes

- I have searched for prior uses of *PreBriefing*... as of 20200125T1818, I like them in Nursing Education: Dana E. Brackney, and Kimberly S. Priode. ‘Creating Context with *Prebriefing*: A Case Example Using Simulation.’ ResearchGate, 11 Nov. 2014, doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.5430/jnep.v5n1p129>.

- And I too liked this cited guidance from Benner, Patricia et al. 2009 presenting ‘four overarching goals for transforming nursing education: 1) implement a sense of situated cognition, for salience and action in particular nursing care situations; 2) integrate clinical and classroom teaching; 3) emphasize clinical reasoning and multiple ways of thinking; and 4) use experiential learning to form a professional identity. All four of these goals were integrated into the design of this simulation learning sequence.’ Brackney, Dana E. and Priode, Kimberly S. 2014, Page 130, Column One, Paragraph Two,
- For my version of **giving feedback** I did not reply to members threads **opting to let members form their alliances of peer-to-peer learning and praise**, I posted a *DeBriefing* after peer-to-peer responses and an *Upshot* review after Grading.
 - In the *DeBriefing* I presented my interpretation of The Call of the Question and answered the Question. If possible I reconnected to the prior assignment(s), attempting to show where we had come from, where we are and where we are going. Here is an example of an *Assignment*, *PreBriefings* and a *DeBriefing*,
 - In the *Upshot* review, I cited to, reflected on and made connections for members posts putting forth ideas and analysis that peers liked and that offered us learning; members *Praise Commentary* showed the way on this.

Praise Commentary

- * Members’ *Praise Commentary* and *discussions of the plausible* were the stars of the discussion boards. The discussions included *plausible Causal story telling*,
- * Pitching one of the core endeavours in any biomedical investigation of an exposure(s) and outcomes relationship is *the discovery of Causality*, pitching *we can design experiments* that seek to show a cause and effect relation, speculating on observing outcomes for differing degrees of exposure to *postulated causal factors*, I interpreted as aiding the class members enthusiasm for and engagement with the discussion forums moving towards causal investigations and away from a “link,” an “association,” a “Correlation” language ambiguousness. See Hernán 2018. Our *Learning Collaboration* tried to take an explicit approach to seek causal studies for our analysis, seeking to identify *critical observations*. Note. ‘I interpreted,’ is a close sibling of a ‘smell test,’ I am counting the number of *uninstructed by me* peer-to-peer responses as a marker of enthusiasm and engagement,
- * Framing *Risk Assessments (RAs)* as addressing exposures to multiple chemical and non-chemical stressors, focusing on the characterization of health risks in vulnerable populations was also a player for enthusiasm and engagement,
- Here is an example of an *Upshot* review for the same Assignment, including excerpts of members posts,

- In a collection of ten assignments, members *Praise Commentary* and *requested members questions* for fellow class members formed the next assignment on two occasions,

Next,

Thanks for reading this, I have a plan to publish notes on teaching, the above will be the first,

- ***A future note on teaching*** will be collaborative, reporting the role of ***Praise Commentary*** for five, six, seven, eight year olds,
- ***On Content***, another ***note*** is in the works, supposedly coming up with the elements of a research proposal, another string in our bows, a three-minute elevator pitch. A key decision will be can the High School Curriculum in the Sciences be both re-designed with references to Health Disparities and Environment Degradation guiding content and still be *The Curriculum* supporting Science AP exams, sure we will be trying for great ***choices and relevancy***.

...

Funding

None

Acknowledgments

Sherrish Holloman EdD, Teachers College Columbia University, Guidance shared, circa 2006 ->
Laura Rigolisi EdD, Teachers College, Columbia University, Guidance shared, circa 2014

Thank you

References

- Benner, Patricia, Sutphen, Molly, Leonard, Victoria, and Day, Lisa. 2009. 'Educating Nurses: A Call for Radical Transformation | Wiley,' Jossey-Bass/Carnegie Foundation for the Advancement of Teaching (December). Accessed December 29, 2019. <https://www.wiley.com/en-us/Educating+Nurses%3A+A+Call+for+Radical+Transformation-p-9780470457962>.
- Brackney, Dana E. and Priode, Kimberly S. 2014. 'Creating context with prebriefing: A case example using simulation.' RESEARCHGATE (November 11). Accessed November 22, 2019. doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.5430/jnep.v5n1p129>. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/268214454_Creating_context_with_prebriefing_A_case_example_using_simulation.

Draft

DCUEVAS1. 2019. 'Discussion Board Best Practices.' INSTRUCTIONAL TECHNOLOGY, St. Edwards University Instructional Technology Blog (March 28). Accessed December 25, 2019. <https://sites.stedwards.edu/instructionaltechnology/2019/03/28/discussion-board-best-practices/>.

Hernán, Miguel A. 2018. 'The C-Word: Scientific Euphemisms Do Not Improve Causal Inference From Observational Data.' *American Journal of Public Health* 108, no. 5 (May): 616. Accessed September 6, 2019. doi:10.2105/AJPH.2018.304337. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5888052/>.

McPhee, John. 2013. 'Draft No. 4.' *The New Yorker* (April 29). ISSN: 0028-792X, accessed November 4, 2015. <http://www.newyorker.com/magazine/2013/04/29/draft-no-4>.

Draft